

University of Novi Sad
**INSTITUTE
OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGY
IN NOVI SAD**

fech
congress

16-18 October, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia

5th

**INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
FOOD TECHNOLOGY,
QUALITY AND SAFETY**

e-ABSTRACT BOOK

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

V INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS “FOOD TECHNOLOGY, QUALITY AND SAFETY”, 16-18 OCTOBER 2024, NOVI SAD, REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Publisher

University of Novi Sad
Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad
Bulevar cara Lazara 1
21000 Novi Sad
Republic of Serbia

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CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

663/664:658.562(048.3)
614.31(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety" (5 ; 2024 ; Novi Sad)

e-Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / 5th International Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety", 16-18 October 2024, Novi Sad ; [main editor Ljubiša Šarić]. - Novi Sad : Institute of Food Technology, 2024

Način pristupa (URL): https://fins.uns.ac.rs/publications/?_sft_publicationss=zbornik. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 22.10.2024.

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

а) Животне намирнице -- Контрола квалитета -- Апстракти б) Животне намирнице -- Хигијена -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155106313

MICROBIOLOGICAL HAZARDS IN CULINARY HERBS AND SPICES

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Microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoa) naturally inhabit the environment. Therefore, contamination of food by microorganisms is not uncommon, and herbs and spices, a food category with a long tradition of use in cooking, are not an exception. Pathogenic microorganisms can seriously endanger health of consumers. One important tool for safeguarding of public health in the European Union is the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF). The aim of the present study was to obtain an insight into microbiological hazards in herbs and spices, both pathogenic and non-pathogenic, as reported in the RASFF database (2011-2023). Out of a total of 848 notifications, 807 were related to pathogenic microorganisms, with products most frequently contaminated by *Salmonella* (694), followed by a much smaller number of cases registering the presence of *Escherichia coli* (83) and *Bacillus cereus* (44). Non-pathogenic contamination of products included presence of moulds or Enterobacteriaceae. The bases for notification were dominantly border controls (62.0%) and official controls on the market (27.2%), while food poisonings cases (0.6%) and consumer complaints (0.2%), although sporadic, are indicators of non 100% functioning of the system. The product most frequently contaminated with microorganisms was pepper (43.2%), while significant numbers of cases were also reported for paprika (7.8%) and basil (5.8%), with the raw materials mainly originated from Brazil (322 consignments, mostly pepper), but also from other countries – India, Vietnam, China etc. Since 76.6% of notifications were characterized as serious public health risks, more than half of the cases resulted in border rejections (54.5%). Substantially smaller proportions of notifications were classified as information (24.2%) and alerts (21.3%). These findings are a significant resource that enables a better understanding of microbiological contamination of spices, thus enabling the improvement of preventive measures and more efficient risk management in the field of food safety.

Keywords: Pathogenic microorganisms, Non-pathogenic microorganisms, Food safety, Public health, RASFF